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METHODS FOR EVALUATING THE PERFORMANCE OF ESL STUDENTS

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Annotation. *The article discusses various methods for evaluating the performance of ESL students in both higher and secondary education systems. Assessment plays a vital role in the teaching process as it helps us understand the progress of our students, evaluate the effectiveness of our teaching strategies, and identify any challenges that may need to be addressed in future lessons. The article highlights three types of assessment: assessment as learning, assessment of learning, and assessment for learning.*

Key words: *assessment, learning process, portfolio, student-teacher conferences, content-based measures.*

Assessment is indeed crucial for understanding students' progress, evaluating teaching strategies, and identifying areas for improvement. It's important to remember that assessments should be tailored to individual students and their unique needs.

Assessment as learning is a student-centered approach that empowers multilingual students by allowing them to actively participate in the assessment process. This strategy promotes students' voices, agency, and identities in the classroom. Multilingual students can engage in assessment as learning in person or virtually by interacting with their peers in their language(s) of choice to: discuss problems of common concern and help design classroom assignments, evaluate oneself and one's peers, seek knowledge in their own ways, pick your preferred means of information intake and expression (e.g., verbal, written, graphic, visual).

By incorporating assessment as learning into the educational process, teachers can create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment that values the diverse linguistic backgrounds of their students. This approach not only helps students better understand their own progress but also fosters a sense of ownership and empowerment in their learning journey.

Discussions between the teacher and the student could lead to the formulation of learning objectives that are acceptable to both parties. Both are well-versed in the academic material and language proficiency criteria that students at each grade level should have mastered by now [Cheng, L. Y. 2006]. During formative assessment, students who speak a language other than English with their teachers use those languages to: implement a criterion-referenced feedback strategy that involves co-creating success criteria and types of acceptable evidence for their work.

Differentiated lessons in both subject matter and language provide immediate responses to student progress or difficulties.

Classroom assessment is shaped by teachers, either independently or as a team at the department or grade level, with student feedback. It's a snapshot of what pupils have learned and accomplished by the end of a specific learning unit. Learning assessment is centered on teacher collaboration with the backing of school or district administrators to determine student improvement over time and is used to:

support students in the creation of portfolios or capstone projects by correlating assessment data with learning objectives recording students' levels of compliance with unit learning standards [Brindley, G. 1998].

When teachers aim to provide their students with as much linguistic and cultural diversity as possible, a comprehensive system that includes assessment as, for, and of learning is essential.

Teachers of multilingual students must evaluate their performance on both linguistic and content-based measures. Academic-language development is not always something that needs to be assessed, therefore teachers must be deliberate about what they examine.

Due of the various criteria that make up a rubric, they can be a useful tool for evaluating pupils' progress. Multilingual students can benefit from the usage of rubrics because they can be used to objectively evaluate students' performance on a variety of assignments and projects. This criterion allows educators to focus solely on the rubric's stated criteria while evaluating students' progress. A rubric can help teachers determine whether or not their students have truly grasped a concept, as opposed to a more subjective approach like a multiple-choice test. Teachers can use the grading scale on a rubric to provide students constructive criticism that will encourage them to reflect on their work, ask questions, get more information, and ultimately produce better results. Students can use the rubric to self-evaluate their work before submitting it for grading, which is another way in which rubrics promote student agency in the learning process. [Assessment Reform Group. 2002]

The teacher can see evidence of the student's effort and learning over a longer time period than with an end-of-unit evaluation, making portfolios a wonderful option for assessing bilingual students. The instructor can then determine whether or not the students "got it" right away and whether or not they were able to "keep it" beyond the end of the course. Multiple examples of student work or evidence of mastery of a concept or standard should be included in a portfolio. Work samples from students could be anything from a writing prompt to a project to a multiple-choice exam. This means that portfolios provide a more accurate depiction of a student's learning process.

Student-teacher conferences are another useful tool for evaluating ELLs. Students benefit from one-on-one conferences because they can demonstrate their knowledge and understanding without the pressure of an exam. The teacher can more easily confine the discussion to the topic at hand during a conference, whether it be subject matter, academic language development, or something else entirely. Each conference may be tailored to the individual needs of each student, giving educators the information they need to better prepare their lessons [Benson, R., & Brack, C. 2010].

All necessary screening and assessment must be made available in both of their languages. The bilingual mind also differs in operation from that of two monolingual minds. Studies have shown that the most effective screening and evaluation methods would be those tailored to the unique needs of bilingual thinkers, capturing their knowledge and skills in both languages. There is a lack of high-quality resources like this, and not enough of them in the necessary languages. Multilingual children's performance on kindergarten entrance tests and other district-mandated monolingual testing is often subpar. The most effective strategy involves tracking a child's progress over time on a number of different measures of their abilities and knowledge. Assessment, in the early years, is not a score but a folder, as we like to put it. Teachers can use the scores and other data in the folder to track a student's development and identify areas where they're struggling.

Portfolio-based assessment is the solution advocated by most specialists. Teachers can collect genuine evidence of students' knowledge and communication skills through portfolios, rather than relying on a single test score or snapshot. Some curricular frameworks include portfolio assessment software, while others sell it separately. Data entry options, prompts, and benchmarks may all be part of such systems.

It is crucial that educators have access to mobile devices throughout the school day in order to record student conversations and behavior [Cassady, J. C., & Gridley, B. E. 2005]. For students learning more than one language, this is a crucial skill since

it allows teachers to better understand what their students are saying when they are speaking a language that is not their native tongue. Because they may be the only adults with whom some bilingual children interact in their home language, it is crucial that bilingual teacher aides be well-prepared to take part in the assessment process.

The input of family members is a valuable resource that should not be overlooked. While it's unlikely that a seventh-grade teacher would inquire about their child's progress in algebra at home, many kindergartners and preschoolers demonstrate language and learning gains at home that might not be apparent in the classroom. In the classroom, young children don't always do what's expected of them. A child's family can help a teacher scaffold their education by providing cultural context and knowledge about the child's interests. Young children will be able to more precisely demonstrate their knowledge and abilities, as well as their readiness for the next step, through the use of several assessments across a variety of activities and times of day.

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